

TEMPERATURE SENSOR BASED ON LIQUID PHASE TRANSITION

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ABSTRACT

A temperature sensor with alarm function based on the temperature-driven liquid phase transition has been designed and fabricated. This chamber-like temperature sensor device consists of a highly stretchable CNFs/ecoflex film as the deformable lid and an aluminum box-like base. 1 mL of water was sealed in the “chamber” and it can vaporize rapidly to induce deformation in the CNFs/ecoflex film when environment temperature reaches its boiling point, resulting in a dramatic increase of resistance in the CNFs/ecoflex film. This temperature sensor shows a high sensitivity of $-0.84\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$ below the boiling temperature of the liquid sealed in the box. Closed to the boiling temperature, significant resistance change is measured, indicating the potential as an alarm system. The response temperature could be controlled by changing the liquid inside the chamber. The cyclic tests indicate good durability. Owing to the advantages of low cost, simple fabrication, and good repeatability, this temperature sensor device has great potential for application as a thermistor or a temperature alarm in food and materials industry.

1 INTRODUCTION

Many research efforts have been made to develop functional sensors to detect ambient conditions, including temperature, [1, 2] moisture[3] and acidity[4]. Temperature, as a fundamental physical parameter, is the prerequisite in the field of fire detection, food and materials storage. Recently, temperature warning sensors based on graphene oxide composite were reported for its rapid response to the flame.[5, 6] Resistance change caused by the reduction of graphene oxide served as the indicator of temperature. However, this reaction is irreversible and those sensors could only be used once. The development of low-cost and reusable temperature sensing and alarm system is still in urgent demand.

To provide a temperature sensor with alarm function, significant resistance change at a trigger temperature is required. But in most thermistors, the resistance value exhibit a linear relationship to temperature with a constant temperature coefficient of resistance (often donated as TCR or α) [1, 2, 7]. In addition, the value of the temperature coefficient of resistance is usually very low (typically lower than $2\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$). The conductive element of a carbon-based thermistor, including nanofibers (CNF),[8, 9] carbon nanotubes (CNT),[10, 11] graphite,[12, 13] graphene[3, 14-16] and reduced graphene oxide (r-GO)[17], also shows good strain sensing capacity. Transferring the trigger temperature input signal into the strain stimulus may be a promising solution to introduce alarm function into a temperature sensor.

Reversible actuator systems based on temperature-driven phase transition provide the possibility of transferring temperature condition into the strain stimulus in the elastomer matrix.[18-20] Zhou et al.[18] reported an electrothermal phase transition actuator consisting of an enclosed cavity made up of highly elastic elastomers and an embedded electrical heater. Water was injected into the cavity and it can vaporize with temperature increasing, making the elastic cavity expand to large deformation.

Inspired by this, we introduced a refillable “chamber” design to fabricate a temperature alarm with high temperature sensitivity based on the phase transition of a liquid. In this sensor device, high thermal sensitivity at trigger temperature is achieved by transferring temperature stimulus into mechanical deformation. Temperature-driven phase transition (water evaporation) is employed here to develop high pressure inside this chamber-like sensor device. Stretchable CNFs/ecoflex film is selected to accommodate the induced high pressure via mechanical deformation and transfer the deformation into the electrical resistance signal. Apart from serving as an excellent temperature sensor, this device also demonstrates potential application as an alarm by a sharply increased signal near the boiling temperature of the water with good cyclic performance.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Materials

The carbon nanofibers (Pyrograf-III, grade PR-24-XT-HHT) used in this study were purchased from Applied Science Inc. The Ecoflex 00-30 silicone rubber was supplied by Smooth-On Inc. Poly(4-vinyl pyridine) (Mn = 10 000) was supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. The high-purity silver paste (Silver Paste Plus) was purchased from SPI Supplies.

Figure 1. Schematic illustrations of the preparation process of CNFs/ecoflex films and assembly of the CNFs/ecoflex sensor device.

2.2 Fabrication of CNFs/ecoflex films

CNFs were dispersed in isopropanol (1 mg/mL) with poly(4-vinyl pyridine) (1 wt% based on CNF) as the dispersing agent. This suspension was sonicated for 30 min by the Sonics VCX-750 Vibra Cell Ultra Sonic Processor (40% amplitude; pulse duration: 5 s on, 5 s off). The dispersed CNFs suspension was sprayed onto the surface of fully cured ecoflex thin films (0.5 mm in thickness, 6 cm × 6 cm in length and width) by a spray gun (Blackridge air brush kit with a needle diameter of 0.3 μm). Ecoflex films with CNF coating were baked in an oven at 90 °C for 2 hours to enhance the adhesion. After that, copper wires were attached, as electrodes, on the two ends of rectangle films with the aid of silver paste. Then another layer of ecoflex was poured and cured on the surface to protect the conductive CNF layer and electrodes. The procedure is illustrated in Figure 1.

2.3 Assembly of the sensor device

As shown in Figure 1, sensor devices were prepared by assembling a round aluminum box (diameter: 50mm, a notch 20 mm in diameter 5 mm in depth is in the center) as the substrate with a round

CNFs/ecoflex film (diameter: 50 mm) as the lid. Another aluminum frame and four pairs of screw and nut were used to fix the film onto the box. It is worth noting that 1 mL of water was injected into the aluminum base before assembly as the liquid to demonstrate the phase transition-induced deformation.

2.4 Characterization

The morphologies of CNFs/ecoflex films were examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (FEI Nova SEM 230). The electromechanical tests were conducted on a conductive CNFs/ecoflex film with the Instron universal testing machine (model 3369) and resistance was recorded via a digital multimeter (34465A, Keysight Technologies). The temperature sensing performance of CNFs/ecoflex films was tested by placing the specimen in an oven with temperature increasing stepwise from 35 to 65 °C (5 °C per step). The temperature of the sensor device was recorded by attaching a thermal couple. The performance of sensor devices as temperature alarms was evaluated by placing the specimen in an oven with temperature increasing from room temperature (25 °C) to 115 °C.

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphology and sensing performance of CNF/ecoflex film

As a result of Van der Waals interaction between the particles, CNFs usually come as highly bundled agglomerates. It is crucial to uniformly disperse the CNFs in the surface of ecoflex silicone rubber to obtain satisfied electrical property. For better dispersion, surfactant Poly(4-vinyl pyridine) (PVP) was employed to assist the formation of a stable CNFs/isopropanol suspension. The morphology of the as-sprayed CNFs/ecoflex film was examined by SEM without gold coating. From Figure 2(a), it could be observed that CNFs dispersed uniformly onto the ecoflex surface with almost no obvious agglomerates. In a magnified image (Figure 2(b)), many CNFs are in contact with each other, as indicated by the red circle. This endows the CNFs/ecoflex with high conductivity.

Figure 2 (a) (b) Typical SEM images of CNFs/ecoflex film. (c) Relative resistance variation of CNFs/ecoflex film under stretching.

To assess the strain-sensing performance of the CNFs/ecoflex conductive film, it was subjected to quasi-static tensile loading. The relative resistance variation of the CNFs/ecoflex film increased continuously with the applied strain (Figure 2 (c)). The strain sensing capacity of this conductive film could be evaluated by the gauge factor (GF, k), [21] [22] which is defined as follows:

$$GF = k = \frac{\Delta R}{R_0} \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta R/R_0$ is the relative resistance variation and ε is the applied strain.

In Figure 2 (c), In the strain range from 0% to 110%, the k value is 0.46 while in the strain range from 110% to 500%, the k value is 1.47. During the phase transition from liquid to gas, the volume of water would increase several times, result in large strain in the upper film preventing water escaping. High stretchability is required for the conductive film to accommodate such high strain. The CNFs/ecoflex

film showed a high stretchability up to 500%, indicating the feasibility of CNFs/ecoflex conductive film as the deformable matrix transfer strain stimulus into temperature stimulus.

3.2 Performance of sensor devices as a temperature alarm

Figure 3(a) is the schematic diagram of the prepared CNFs/ecoflex sensor device. A chamber-like sensor device is assembled with a deformable CNFs/ecoflex film as the lid and 1 mL water has been sealed in the chamber. When the whole sensor device is heated to the temperature at the boiling point of water, the water inside the chamber is boiled to steam. The gas pressure inside the chamber caused by the phase transition of water increases rapidly, leading to the extension of the ecoflex film (Figure 3 (b)).

The conductive rectangle CNFs layer is in the middle of the ecoflex film to transfer the deformation into an electrical resistance signal. The temperature sensing performance of the CNFs/ecoflex sensor device was evaluated and results are shown in Figure 3(c). The sensitivity of the temperature sensor is normally given by TCR [23] :

$$\alpha = \frac{R_t - R_i}{R_i \Delta T} \quad (2)$$

where R_t and R_i are the resistance of the sensor at t °C and i °C, ΔT is the deviation in temperature (t °C) from the reference temperature (i °C).[24]

From the inset picture of figure 3(c), the relative resistance change of the conductive CNFs/ecoflex film decrease in the temperature range from 25 to 75 °C due to the semi-conductive charge transport of CNFs where the high temperature facilitated the charge carrier mobility and diminished the resistance. [25] The temperature sensitivity of the CNFs/ecoflex film is estimated to be $-0.84\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$, which is more than twice as much as that of a standard commercial platinum temperature sensor ($0.39\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$),[26] indicating the exceptional temperature sensitivity of the CNFs/ecoflex film. Apart from the high temperature sensitivity, the relative resistance variation exhibit a linear relationship to temperature with an R^2 at 0.999. Then the relative resistance variation skyrockets at $\sim 99^{\circ}\text{C}$ due to the quick expansion of ecoflex film under increasing gas pressure. This significant resistance signal indicates that this sensor device holds great potential as a temperature alarm. By changing the liquid inside the chamber, we can get a device that can be used as an alarm for different temperatures.

Figure 3. Schematic diagrams of the CNFs/ecoflex sensor device at room temperature (a) and the boiling point of water (b), (c) The relative resistance variation of CNFs/ecoflex sensor devices (film thickness: 0.72 mm) upon heating.

3.3 Cyclic performance

The reputability of the CNFs/ecoflex sensor device was evaluated by the cyclic resistance-

temperature test and results were recorded in Figure 4. Although the reactive resistance variation curves exhibit a slight drift in the second and third cycle, compared to the initial one, all cycles showed a similar trade of temperature dependence on resistance value, indicating the thermal-related resistance is reputable and the sensor could be reused.

Figure 4. The relative resistance variations of CNFs/ecoflex sensor device under cyclic heating.

4 CONCLUSION

In summary, we have designed and fabricated phase transition-based temperature sensor with low-cost commercial materials. This temperature sensor shows a relatively high temperature sensitivity as $-0.84\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$. Apart from working as a thermistor, this sensor device also showed promising capacity as a temperature alarm with great reversibility. By transferring the temperature condition of the environment into the strain stimulus via phase transition of water, this chamber-like temperature sensor exhibited alarm function with dramatic resistance increase at a given temperature. The trigger temperature of the alarm sensor could be adjusted via refilling liquids with different boiling points into the chamber. We think that the phase transition-based alarm system could have potential application in monitoring ambient temperature and indicating the trigger temperature in the food and agriculture industry.

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